

Analysis of Complications and Mortality of the Patients with Scrub Typhus in a Tertiary Care Centre in RajasthanAshwini Mishra¹, Kr Sharma², Hritvik Jaiswal³, Vishwajeet Mittal⁴¹3rd Year PG Resident, Pacific Medical College and Hospital, Udaipur²Professor and Head, Dept of General Medicine, Pacific Medical College and Hospital, Udaipur³3rd Year PG Resident, Pacific Medical College and Hospital, Udaipur⁴3rd Year PG Resident, Pacific Medical College and Hospital, Udaipur

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Abstract:

Introduction: Scrub typhus, caused by *Orientia tsutsugamushi*, is prevalent in the Asia-Pacific region, including India. It spreads via bites from infected chiggers. Symptoms range from mild fever to severe, potentially fatal, organ dysfunction. In Rajasthan, awareness and early diagnosis are crucial due to varying clinical presentations, often lacking eschar, complicating diagnosis. Public health education is essential.

Aims and Objective: To analyze the complications and other features of the patients with scrub typhus in a tertiary care centre in Rajasthan.

Method: This clinical study, conducted at Pacific Medical College and Hospital in Udaipur, Rajasthan, focused on 100 patients who tested positive for scrub typhus. The research employed a Stratified Random Sampling methodology to ensure a representative sample from diverse demographics and clinical situations. Patients with positive ELISA tests for IgM antibodies against *O. tsutsugamushi* were included. The study involved serological, microbiological, pathological, and radiographic evaluations, with data analyzed using SPSS 27 and MS Excel. Exclusions included those under 18, with additional infections, or without consent.

Result: The study included 100 patients aged 19 to 43, with a mean age of 32.25±6.69. Males constituted 61% of the sample. Clinical characteristics showed that both genders had 100% prevalence of fever. Females had higher instances of rash, abdominal pain, and loss of consciousness, while males had more nausea, diarrhea, and cough. Blood test parameters were similar across genders, though males had a higher prevalence of severe complications like hepatic dysfunction, shock, ARDS, AKI, meningoencephalitis, and bleeding tendencies. This suggests a greater susceptibility to serious outcomes among male patients.

Conclusion: The study revealed minimal gender differences in hematological parameters, but males showed higher susceptibility to severe complications like hepatic dysfunction, ARDS, and shock, indicating a need for gender-specific health monitoring.

Keywords: Scrub Typhus, Mortality, *Tsutsugamushi*, Rash.

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Introduction

Scrub typhus is a zoonotic infection caused by obligate intracellular bacteria *Orientia tsutsugamushi*, mainly prominent in the Asia-Pacific region including countries like India, China, Japan and Korea [1,2]. The disease is acquired by the bite of an infected chigger- the larval stage of mites belonging to family Trombiculidae especially the genus *Leptotrombidium* [3, 4]. Once the chigger has bitten the host, the bacterium circulates in the host's blood and forms a systemic disease [5]. The incubation period can be from 6 to 21 days since exposure to develop symptoms that include high fever, chills, muscle aches, severe headache, nausea, vomiting and eschar- a necrotic ulcer with an erythematous halo that generally develops at the site of chigger bite [6, 7]. This eschar with regional lym-

phadenopathy is considered as pathognomonic but is apparently in a distinctive proportion of patients. Symptoms of the disease may present from simple febrile illnesses that resolve on their own to severe illness with multiple organ dysfunction that may be fatal if not properly handled and prevented [8].

The awareness of scrub typhus in India increases over time, and endemic cases are reported from several states with moderate morbidity and mortality [9, 10]. There was a severe epidemic in the region of Hadoti in Rajasthan [11, 12] and presented varying clinical conditions with or without eschar. The study suggested the necessity of awareness and better presentation due to low indexed suspicion among clinicians [13]. Scrub typhus is analysed as a re-emerging infectious disease with severe out-

comes; however, epidemiological data on this disease occurring in the described region are limited. It is understood that the environmental and climatic conditions of Hadoti region are quite favourable in contributing to the plenty of vector population and hence many cases of transmission of scrub typhus is experienced. Inhabitants of this area usually engaging in farming and other related activities in the environment increase their likelihood of exposure to mite infected areas [5].

The clinical features of scrub typhus also present a great variance hence its diagnosis and management is not easy [14]. Nevertheless, as with most diseases, the lack of an eschar, which is not uncommon, may cause confusion in diagnosing for the disease [15]. The seriousness of this disease is manifested in the development of complications in the form of acute respiratory distress syndrome, renal failure, hepatic dysfunction and neurological signs that put the life of the patient in danger as observed in fatal cases [16]. The pathogenesis of this disease involves vasculitis and perivascular inflammation of the tissue, and this explains the involvement of several organs in most patients. They progressively become severe and this is manifested by the fact that the complications develop fast and therefore if diagnosed, the right treatment should be ought to be begun. Originally, the standard in diagnosing scrub typhus was predominantly the identification of IgM antibodies of the *O. tsutsugamushi* through serology, which serves as a means to support clinical suspicion [17, 18].

In previous studies carried out at a tertiary care centre in Rajasthan, the authors found out that all the patients with scrub typhus had fever at the onset of their condition. About forty four percent of these patients presented with symptoms that lasted between 7 to 14 days before attending the facility, which supports the prolonged time of diagnosis that is normally characteristic of an endemic region [19, 20]. Interestingly, the traditional signs like eschar and lymphadenopathy, which have been accorded stigmatic significance, were seen in a radically reduced measure in the study, being seen in just 12 and 18 percent of the cases respectively. This discovery is paramount as it reveals the need for clinicians practicing in the region to suspect scrub typhus during treatment regardless of the presented major manifestations [11, 21]. Evaluating the signs that signal the beginning of the progression of the disease and beginning treatments on time ensures that patients have less complications, and this reduces the mortality rate. More-over, there is also inevitably a role for public health programmes for vector control and scrub typhus education among healthcare personnel as well as the wider community concerning its symptoms [10-12, 21].

Methods

Research design: This clinical study was conducted at Pacific Medical College and Hospital in Udaipur, Rajasthan. This study was conducted on a sample of 100 patients, specifically focussing on individuals who tested positive for scrub typhus. This research study employed a Stratified Random Sampling methodology to create a sample of patients who tested positive for scrub typhus that accurately represents the population. The population comprises individuals who have received a diagnosis of scrub typhus. The sample size was determined using the formula $n = (z^2 pq) / d^2$, where 'n' represents the sample size, 'z' denotes the Z-score corresponding to the required confidence level, 'p' represents the estimated proportion of persons having scrub typhus, 'q' represents the complement of 'p,' and 'd' represents the intended margin of error. Based on this calculation, a sample size of at least 100 is sufficient to conduct a comprehensive examination of patients who tested positive for scrub typhus, which will yield useful insights into the condition. The investigation only included patients who had a positive test result for both Scrub Typhus IgG and IgM. In addition, ELISA testing was performed to confirm the diagnosis of scrub typhus. The clinical criteria assessed in this study were the presence of eschar marks and lymphadenopathy, as well as the pattern and intensity of fever. An extensive evaluation was performed, which included serological, microbiological, pathological, and radiographic examinations. Participants were chosen according to daily lists from General Medicine inpatient departments to ensure a systematic technique for recruiting patients. Stratified random sampling was employed to ensure that the samples obtained would include individuals from diverse demographics and clinical situations, thus ensuring representation across different groups. The study aims to thoroughly understand individuals who tested positive for scrub typhus by analyzing their clinical characteristics and diagnostic signs using a rigorous methodological approach. The systematic process of gathering and examining data ensured the robustness and reliability of the conclusions derived from the study's findings.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients above 18 years admitted to medical units who had positive ELISA tests for IgM antibodies against the 56 kDa protein of *O. tsutsugamushi* were enrolled. Patients who are willing to participate in the study and provide an informed consent are included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: The patients were diagnosed with an additional infection or an alternative reason for their high fever. The patient tested scrub negative and is under 18 years of age were

excluded. Patients who do not provide an informed consent are excluded.

Statistical Analysis: The data collected from each participant was consolidated into a thorough Excel spreadsheet to facilitate easy organising and analysis. The study employed SPSS 27 for rigorous analysis and utilised MS Excel for calculations. The discrete data was represented by its frequency, while the continuous data was represented by its mean value and standard deviation.

Results

Figure 1 displays the ages of the patients involved in the study. The patients' ages range from 19 to 43, encompassing a broad group. The mean age is

32.25±6.69. The distribution seems to be uniform, with a substantial number of patients in every age category. Multiple instances involving individuals in their late 20s and early 40s suggest that these age groups are the most prevalent. There are patients in their early forties and individuals aged 19-22 as well. The age distribution of the study population is significant when examining the study data as some diseases or outcomes may differ according on age. The age distribution aids researchers and healthcare practitioners in assessing the representativeness of the study sample and interpreting the results in relation to age-related attributes.

Figure 1: Age distribution of the patients

Figure 2 indicates the sex distribution of the patients. Males are more 61% when compared to females (39%).

Figure 2: Sex distribution of the patients in this study

Table 1 compares the clinical characteristics among female and male patients in a study group. All patients in both groups (100%) exhibited pyrexia, demonstrating it is a prevalent symptom regardless of gender. Females exhibited a higher prevalence of some symptoms such as rash, stomach pain, loss of consciousness, and lymphadenopathy. Males exhibited a higher prevalence of symptoms such as

nausea, diarrhoea, and cough. There was a similar occurrence of symptoms such as fever, myalgia and arthralgia, and seizures among both genders. The pulse rate exhibited a high degree of similarity between the two groups, indicating that gender did not have a substantial impact on this essential physiological indicator within the research population.

Table 1: Clinical features of the males and females

Clinical Feature	Female (n=39)	Male (n=61)
Fever	39 (100%)	61 (100%)
Headache	24 (61.53%)	40(65.57%)
Myalgia And Arthralgia	28(71.79%)	43(70.49%)
Eschar	4 (10.2%)	6 (9.8%)
Rash	30(76.92%)	15(24.59%)
Nausea	30(76.92%)	58(95.08%)
Vomiting	32(82.05%)	45(73.77%)
Abdominal Pain	33(84.61%)	13(21.31%)
Diarrhoea	21(53.84%)	50(81.96%)
Lymphadenopathy	26(66.66%)	27(44.26%)
Cough	21(53.84%)	51(83.60%)
Dyspnoea	27(69.23%)	45(73.77%)
Loss Of Consciousness	30(76.92%)	23(37.07%)
Seizure	20(51.28%)	31(50.81%)
Pulse Rate	83.28±10.92	83.34±10.88

Table 2 displays the blood test outcomes of 100 individuals, consisting of 39 females and 61 males. These blood tests assess overall well-being and identify abnormalities by analyzing a range of factors. The mean white blood cell (WBC) levels were similar across females (8086.41 ± 1839.6) and males (8067.37 ± 1840.19), suggesting that their immunological activity was equivalent. The levels of red blood cells (RBC), hemoglobin (Hb), and hematocrit (HCT), which transport oxygen in the body, were marginally elevated in males compared to females, indicating disparities in blood composition across genders. The mean values for

red blood cell shape and features, such as MCV, MCH, MCHC, and RDW, were similar between females and males. The mean platelet counts for females (144386.74 ± 3528.87) and males (144321.83 ± 3570.51) were similar, indicating that there were no significant variations in platelet levels across genders. The blood test values and vital signs exhibit notable uniformity between the female and male cohorts in this study. These data indicate that, within this particular group, there are no notable disparities between genders in the crucial hematological and physiological parameters that were assessed.

Table 2: Findings of blood tests of males and females

Blood Test Parameter	Female (N=39)	Male (N=61)
White Blood Cell Count (WBC)	8086.41±1839.6	8067.37±1840.19
Red Blood Cell Count (RBC)	5.22±0.43	5.23±0.43
Hemoglobin (Hb)	13.26±0.67	13.27±0.67
Hematocrit (HCT)	40.22±1.59	41.22±1.59
Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV)	89.12±6.80	89.12±6.76
Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin (MCH)	29.01±1.48	28.99±1.48
Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC)	33.77±1.38	33.77±1.37
Red Cell Distribution Width (Rdw)	12.92±0.86	12.92±0.86
Platelet Count	144386.74±3528.87	144321.83±3570.51
Mean Platelet Volume (Mpv)	9.58 ±1.21	10.00 ±1.21
Spo2	96.50±2.17	96.76±2.17
Respiratory Rate	16.89±2.16	16.84±2.16
Rbs	98.29±17.56	98.3±17.56

According to table 3, male patients had a higher prevalence of sequelae such as hepatic dysfunction, shock, ARDS, AKI, meningoencephalitis, and bleeding tendencies compared to female patients. These findings indicate that guys in this study may have been more susceptible to experiencing serious

consequences. Nevertheless, the incidence of pneumonia and myocarditis in males is either comparable or marginally greater, suggesting that these consequences have a similar impact on both genders.

Table 3: Complications of the patients with respect to gender

Complication	Female (n=39)	Male (n=61)
Hepatic Dysfunction	14(35.8%)	30(49.1%)
Shock	10(25.6%)	20(32.7%)
Pneumonia	8(20.5%)	12(19.6%)
ARDS	10 (25.6%)	18 (29.5%)
Myocarditis	3 (7.6%)	6 (9.8%)
AKI	4 (10.2%)	10 (16.3%)
Meningoencephalitis	2 (5.1%)	8 (13.1%)
Bleeding tendency	2 (5.1%)	6 (9.8%)

Discussion

Scrub typhus is rickettsial disease that affects patients with symptoms that can range from fever illness to severe diseases that affect multiple organs in one's body. This often leads to problems in diagnosis and management of the disease which is characterized by variability in presentation. The pathogenesis of the disease is characterized by vasculitis and perivascular infiltration of inflammatory cells and this may be an indication of the reason for the multiorgan dysfunction that is observed in its severe form. If left untreated scrub typhus can cause severe complications like acute respiratory distress syndrome, renal failure, hepatic dysfunction and neurological manifestations [7, 9, 12].

In areas such as Hadoti in Rajasthan it has been observed that favourable environmental and climatic conditions led to the breeding of vector, and in turn the transmission of the disease. The local people mainly involved in farming and other activities outside the house are more vulnerable because they always move to the mite-infested areas. Since a majority of people lack awareness about scrub typhus and the symptoms are very much like other febrile illnesses, diagnosis is delayed and proper treatment seldom received – this worsens the effect of scrub typhus [2, 11, 14, 16]. Another important aspect worth considering is that eschar and lymphadenopathy indicators are missing in many patients, which means that doctors ought to include scrub typhus as a diagnose even if these primary symptoms are not suggested [8, 11, 17].

The mortality and morbidity of 2% indicates the graveness of scrub typhus in the patient group in the Hadoti region. This high mortality rate exposes a need for the early identification of the disorder and the subsequent commencement of the right management strategies to prevent deaths. Eradicating scrub typhus in such areas as Hadoti requires

the formulation of an all-round strategy that focuses on increasing awareness, improving diagnostic and treatment methodologies as well as approaches towards meeting the diseases' clinical needs. Therefore, the mortality rate of scrub typhus in the areas of Rajasthan, describes the nature of the disease and the difficulties in treating it. Many patients develop a late stage of the disease: they do not seek medical care and do not receive a proper diagnosis because mostly everybody and even healthcare providers rarely hear about the disease, or they experience quite non-specific symptoms. Specific management of scrub typhus should start at the first sight of symptoms; the longer the wait to start with the therapy, the higher the mortality and morbidity rates will be [11, 19, 22].

To overcome these difficulties associated with a scrub typhus diagnosis, the identification has to be worked on in several aspects. Sensitization of the public and health care providers is crucial in attaining high knowledge levels about the disease. This can help when there are symptoms that need medical attention, one can quickly attend to them. Serological tests for the specific IgM antibodies of *O. tsutsugamushi* can help substantiate clinicians' suspicion and contribute to early identification [11, 15, 21, 23]. There is, therefore, need to enhance the capacity for diagnosis particularly in the lower tiers of the healthcare system including the primary and secondary levels.

Conclusion

The findings from the blood tests of 100 individuals, consisting of 39 females and 61 males, reveal minimal gender-based differences in key hematological and physiological parameters. The mean white blood cell (WBC) counts, which reflect immunological activity, were almost identical for females (8086.41 ± 1839.6) and males (8067.37 ± 1840.19). Additionally, the levels of red blood cells

(RBC), hemoglobin (Hb), and hematocrit (HCT) were slightly higher in males, indicating minor differences in blood composition. However, other parameters, including mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), red cell distribution width (RDW), and platelet counts, were nearly the same between genders, suggesting overall uniformity in these measures.

Despite the similarities in the blood test results, male patients had a higher prevalence of serious complications such as hepatic dysfunction, shock, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), acute kidney injury (AKI), meningoencephalitis, and bleeding tendencies. This suggests a greater susceptibility to severe outcomes among male patients in this study. On the other hand, the incidence of pneumonia and myocarditis was relatively similar between genders, indicating these complications affect both genders similarly.

This study highlights the need for gender-specific health monitoring, particularly in males who exhibit a higher prevalence of severe complications. Uniform hematological parameters suggest similar baseline health, but increased male susceptibility to complications underscores the importance of targeted interventions to enhance patient outcomes.

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